

BRINGING SPACE TECHNOLOGY TO MINING – BIOSENSORS FOR HEALTH MONITORING IN REAL TIME AS A MODERN MANAGEMENT PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT. Nowadays, mining industry is striving to be regarded as a modern and highly-technological field with no negative connotation to its name. The human factor is constantly increasing in significance, making mining industry more people oriented, and more and more efforts are being made to bring modern technologies into service and help create safer work environment. Utilising new types of biosensors provides remote health monitoring of workers in mining industry, thus enabling the real time monitoring of vitals of a person, permitting timely medical care and preventing long-term negative exposures. In this regard, the use of flexible, lightweight and wearable biosensors is seen as very convenient and patient-friendly in work environment without interfering with the daily activities. In this study we present a non-enzymatic glucose sensors based on ZnO nanoparticles prepared by a laser ablation in liquid method.

Key words: ZnO nanoparticles, laser ablation, biosensors, glucose

Introduction

Over the last decade, mining industry has been constantly developing in terms of engaging new technologies in the field. Different approaches employing non-conventional eco-friendly techniques such as phytomining and unmanned aerial systems are gradually being utilised to replace traditional mining processes. At the same time, the importance of the human factor is constantly increasing and companies around the world are now investing in creating a safe work environment with the aid of the latest technology achievements.

Space programmes were always the driving force for the development of cutting-edge technologies. The concept of “lab-on-chip” devices is a prime candidate for the use in space missions due to the specific requirements for such tasks (small volume, lightweight, as well as low sample and reagent consumption). Designing a “true” lab-on-chip system requires integration in a single device of sample handling, analytical detection and signal transduction that would permit remote monitoring and analysis.

As an example, chemiluminescence (CL) was proposed as a detection method for chemical and biological samples (Nascetti, 2016) since it does not require excitation source which makes it suitable for miniaturised devices. Based on this study, as well as on similarities in work environment (such as hazardous and remote location with the lack of immediate medical assistance), we considered the implementation of small and wearable devices (Yang and Cheng, 2020) that can monitor the health of mine workers in real time underground. For this purpose, the so-called biosensors could be very promising candidates, that is, devices that respond to some biological or chemical reactions by producing a signal proportional to the concentration of the target analyte in the reaction.

A biosensor usually incorporates five parts: (i) an **analyte** (a substance, usually a biological molecule whose concentration is to be monitored, e.g. glucose); (ii) a **bioreceptor** (an agent that specifically recognises the analyte and generates a signal, such as light, heat, pH, charge, or mass change, etc., the so called bio-recognition); (iii) a

transducer (which converts the generated signal into either optical or electrical signals proportional to the analyte concentration); (iv) **electronics** (which consists of complex electronic circuitry that converts the signal to digital form); and (v) a **display** (which is either a computer or a printer that displays numbers and results (Bhalla, 2016)).

Biosensors can be successfully utilised in some disease monitoring, drug discovery, detection of pollutants or disease-causing micro-organisms and markers that are indicators of a disease in bodily fluids (blood, urine, saliva, sweat, see: Bhalla et al., 2016). Different detection methods were reported, with those based on electrochemical technique being preferred owing to their swift response, high selectivity, high sensitivity and stability. Usually, enzymatic sensors are utilised due to their high selectivity based on biochemical reactions with a metabolite, however, they suffer from the complexity of immobilisation, the density of the enzyme layer and a relatively poor durability over time (working cycles) (Wang, 2008; Tremey et al., 2017). To overcome these obstacles, research explored the possibility of nonenzymatic glucose sensors as electrochemical biosensors (Hwang et al., 2018). Sensors of this type have low costs, relatively simple manufacturing and are stable over time (Dhara and Mahapatra, 2018). The electroactive part of nonenzymatic sensors usually involves metals, metal alloys and transition-metal oxides (because of their high catalytic activity). Electrodes can be deposited on a flexible support (for example, by electrodeposition), thus creating a sensor device that can be firmly and closely attached to a body surface and monitor analytes (glucose) in the sweat over a long period of time (Li et al., 2021).

Analysis of the literature reveals that sensors proposed so far: (i) are not sensitive enough, (ii) often demonstrate low selectivity, and (iii) are not available yet as a commercial product ready to use (Bandodkar et al., 2019). That is why new approaches, as well as new materials, are actively sought these days to accelerate the field and develop wearable sensors for non-invasive detection of glucose and other biomedical applications (Mani et al., 2017).

Body sweat is an epidermal fluid containing various metabolites, electrolytes and trace elements released from the

body. In contrast to other biological fluids (such as blood, serum, plasma), sweat is excreted and can be collected non-invasively, and thus can be easily used for diagnostic tests. Numerous biomarkers available in the sweat were shown to reveal the physiological status of blood, which is why they can be a signal of our body functions and total fitness. Sweat contains numerous biomolecules, of which the most abundant are glucose and lactates. And because of the remarkable demand for the development of non-invasive health-test methods, the latter two markers are of very high research interest as analytes these days (Choi et al., 2018; Currano et al., 2018). Therefore, development of fast, flexible, wearable sensors for non-invasive sweat analysis is highly desirable for the society and is a real 'hot topic' nowadays.

Laser ablation in liquid (LAL) is a convenient and efficient technique to produce diverse nanoparticles (NPs) at laboratory scale (Niu et al., 2010; Zeng et al., 2012; Kondo et al., 2017; Mintcheva et al., 2018). In this approach, a laser beam is typically focused on a solid target, producing plasma, vapour or molten metal drops which then react with the liquid medium and give rise to NPs of metal oxides, sulphides or carbides. Compared with conventional chemical methods, LAL is a simple and green technique that offers facile one-step synthesis of NPs, operates in a minimum volume of liquid medium and often permits to control both chemical composition and morphology of produced NPs (Niu et al., 2010; Zeng et al., 2012; Kondo et al., 2017; Mintcheva et al., 2018). Because of very high temperature gradients and quenching rates in the ablation zone, the method often allows for production of NPs with metastable phases and/or unique morphologies and properties, which is of direct interest for the present research as such NPs cannot be prepared by other methods (Niu et al., 2010; Zeng et al., 2012; Kondo et al., 2017; Mintcheva et al., 2018). Recently, LAL-produced nanomaterials proved to be efficient chemiresistive gas sensors at room temperature (Kondo T. et al., 2017; Mintcheva N. et al., 2018). That is why, incorporating such nanomaterials as sensing elements into wearable sensors for biomedical use looks very timely and promising.

To achieve the above challenging goal, we planned the following key progressive objectives: (i) preparation of nanomaterials via laser ablation in liquid; (ii) their separation and characterisation; (iii) fabrication of flexible and wearable sensing electrode; (iv) testing of the newly prepared sensors as detectors of glucose ions in sweat by performance of cyclic voltammetry measurements. The results of each of these stages were described and presented in this paper.

Method and Materials

Preparation of ZnO NPs.

ZnO NPs were prepared by irradiation of Zn plate (99.5% purity, 2 mm thick) with nanosecond pulsed laser (Nd: YAG) with the following parameters: 532 nm as wavelength, 10 Hz as frequency, 50 mJ/pulse and 45 min as pulse energy and ablation time, respectively. The procedure was performed using conditions previously described by Gavrilenko et al. (2019). The Zn plate was pre-treated by consecutive washing in acetone, ethanol and pure water for 180 s and then immersed in quartz cuvette (30 mm x 30 mm x 50 mm, wall thickness of 2 mm) filled with 20 ml of pure water. The obtained dispersion was centrifuged for 10 min (16,500 rpm) and the ZnO NPs were washed with pure water three times

and redispersed and used for further analysis of the prepared material.

Glucose sensing measurements

To test the electrochemical activity of the obtained ZnO NPs, we used a three-electrode system (PalmSens4, potentiostat/galvanostat/impedance analyser) where ZnO NPs (deposited on glass carbon electrode, GCE) act as a working electrode (Ag/AgCl and Pt are used as a reference and a counter electrode, respectively). The ZnO NPs were applied as a thick paste (in ethanol) after sonication for 15 min at room temperature. For the electrochemical experiments, a solution of artificial sweat was prepared (from Nanochemazone, Canada and 0.1 M NaCl) and then used in all glucose sensing experiments.

Results and Discussion

The ZnO NPs prepared in pure water were separated by centrifugation, washed three times and characterised by UV-Vis spectroscopy and SEM. The spectrum of diluted dispersion of ZnO NPs taken on Shimadzu UV-2450 spectrometer is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectrum of ZnO NPs

The absorption maximum observed at 345 nm is attributed to the presence of nanosized ZnO and the position of the maximum is related to the particle size (band gap energy transition).

The formation of ZnO NPs is also confirmed by SEM analysis which showed two fraction of particles, with average sizes around 150-200 nm diameter and around 50-100 nm (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. SEM image of ZnO NPs separated from water dispersion

Since the laser-prepared ZnO NPs were free of any surfactants (because no surfactants or any reagents were used during laser ablation in water), they were expected to be suitable for the active part of biosensors due to lack of interference with the surface chemistry in redox processes.

The potential of ZnO NPs as a working electrode in glucose sensing in sweat was tested by cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements, the results being displayed in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. CV curves in artificial sweat solution (0.1 M NaCl) with different concentration of glucose (2; 4; 6; 8 and 10 mM) recorded for working electrode modified with ZnO NPs.

Direct electrochemistry of the electrode (modified with ZnO NPs) in artificial sweat revealed a pair of well-defined redox peaks which are characteristic for glucose. Their intensity is seen to change with the concentration of glucose, which shows good catalytic activity for glucose oxidation. Figure 3 shows the CV of ZnO-GCE versus different glucose concentrations ranging from 2 to 10 mM. It is intriguing that the peak current decreased in a linear manner with glucose concentration. Other authors also observed similar behaviour for glucose oxidase immobilised on hexamine ruthenium (III) chloride $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ containing a nitrocellulose strip for urine glucose. They also demonstrated a linear decrease in peak current with increasing glucose density (Park et al., 2005). Possible reasons could be explained by mixing of analyte glucose sample in bulk electrolyte artificial sweat solution and its dependent electrochemical reaction at the ZnO-GCE electrode, which probably influenced the concentration variation in oxidation of produced H_2O_2 and reduction of O_2 . In addition, air saturation in artificial sweat solution and the existence of interferents in the sweat samples may have decreased the peak electrocatalytic current.

Based on the obtained results, the next step would be to prepare a biosensor which is flexible, lightweight and durable. The sensing part would include a ZnO NPs-GCE working electrode able to detect glucose in sweat. Figure 4A shows schematically the preparation of such a prototype (whose photo is presented in Figure 4B), with the following steps:

- Preparation of a shadow mask to deposit contact electrodes Au/Ti or Ag via sputtering or thermal evaporation technique.
- Preparation of a flexible poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) sheet with a thickness of about 1 mm, which is to serve as the base of a wearable sensor device.

- Drop-cast of Ag/AgCl ink which will play the role of a reference electrode.

Fig. 4. Schematic presentation of preparation of biosensor device based on ZnO NPs-GCE (A) and a picture of prototype of same biosensor (B).

- Sputtering of Au metal which will serve as a counter electrode.
- Drop-cast of ZnO nanomaterial prepared by laser ablation which serves as the working electrode.

Conclusions

The present study demonstrated the successful employment of ZnO nanoparticles (NPs) produced by laser ablation in water for electrochemical oxidation of glucose. The NPs were then used for the preparation of ZnO NPs-GCE as a working electrode for electrochemical detection of glucose in artificial sweat solution. The CV measurements demonstrated changes in the current peak intensity with the concentration of glucose, confirming the possibility of using this sensor for the preparation of flexible wearable device. Steps in that direction were made by optimising a procedure and preparing a thin transparent flexible poly(dimethylsiloxane), PDMS, substrate, which will serve as support for the electrochemical biosensor. The flexibility of the PDMS sheet will provide excellent contact with the natural curves on the human skin texture, thus enabling good contact between the tested fluid, sweat, and the working electrode of the device.

This modern concept for “lab-on-chip” applied in space technologies is very suitable for the mining industry as well. The small size and light weight of the sensor under development will not interfere with the working process and its durability will permit remote monitoring in real time for a long period. Such flexible and wearable biosensors can provide great opportunity for companies to invest in the work environment and well-being of their employees, which will lead

to new and improved perception of the mining industry, increasing its attractiveness in terms of safety.

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